

A Musculoskeletal-Inspired Soft–Rigid Hybrid Tendon-Driven Continuum Robot with Integrated Friction-Aware Modeling and Experimental Validation

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Abstract

Tendon-driven continuum robots (TDCRs) are increasingly deployed in confined and contact-rich environments, yet rigid segmented TDCRs typically face a trade-off between positioning accuracy and safe physical compliance. This work presents a musculoskeletal-inspired soft–rigid hybrid TDCR that integrates a cast silicone layer with 3D-printed rigid units to balance precision, payload capability, and interaction safety. The robot has a 10 mm outer diameter and a 3 mm central lumen for through-lumen instrumentation (e.g., Electromagnetic tracker, biopsy forceps). We report the robot’s design, fabrication workflow, and control, and develop a quasi-static modeling framework that incorporates tendon friction and external tip loading. The model reproduces experimentally observed trends in tip deflection and curvature, and we quantify tip position and orientation errors under representative actuation and loading conditions. We further characterize payload capacity, hysteresis, and durability, and demonstrate fine manipulation tasks enabled by the central lumen, including accurate target grasping with biopsy forceps while maintaining motion accuracy under load.

Keywords: Continuum Robots; Hybrid Soft-Rigid Design; Tendon-Driven Actuation; Kinetostatic Modeling

1 Introduction

Minimally invasive procedures and Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery (NOTES) place stringent requirements on surgical tools, demanding a level of dexterity and adaptability that parallels biological appendages. Instruments must navigate tortuous anatomical pathways and manipulate delicate tissues while preserving surrounding functions. Conventional rigid-link robots often fail to meet these demands due to their inability to achieve the biomimetic kinematics required to conform to unstructured environments. To bridge this gap, bio-inspired compliant mechanisms and continuum robots have emerged as a pivotal class of solutions. By mimicking the morphological properties

of hyper-redundant biological systems, such as elephant trunks or cephalopod tentacles, these robots achieve continuous deformation and passive compliance. [1, 2, 3]. This inherent flexibility, characterized by a distributed compliance along their backbone, enables safer interaction with the environment and superior maneuverability compared to traditional discrete-joint mechanisms [4, 5, 6].

Within this broader family, continuum robots driven by tendons, concentric pre-curved tubes, or fluidic actuators have been intensively studied over the past decade [1, 7]. TDCRs employ tendons routed through or around a flexible backbone to generate bending moments and are attractive for medical applications because they can be scaled down, integrate multiple segments, and be manufactured using relatively simple processes [1, 3]. Concentric-tube robots, in contrast, rely on multiple nested superelastic tubes with programmed pre-curvature and have demonstrated highly dexterous motion at catheter-like diameters, but they often involve complex interactions between tubes and are sensitive to manufacturing tolerances [2]. Soft continuum robots based on elastomeric bodies with pneumatic or hydraulic chambers offer extreme compliance and can conform to delicate tissue surfaces, but they typically exhibit limited load capacity and strong hysteresis [4, 5, 6, 8].

The clinical impact of continuum and soft robots has already been demonstrated in several domains. In orthopedics, for instance, a continuum manipulator combined with a bendable medical screw has been used to deliver curved drilling trajectories that would be impossible with straight tools, potentially improving fixation while reducing invasiveness [9]. In other work, continuum manipulators and compliant mechanisms have been designed to provide controlled force profiles and to maintain safe contact with tissues under uncertainty [10, 11]. These examples underline that the mechanical structure, material choice, and control strategy must be co-designed to meet the stringent requirements of surgical environments. Soft robotics has further expanded the design space by introducing robots made predominantly from silicones, hydrogels, and other low-modulus materials [4, 5]. Such soft continuum manipulators can wrap around obstacles, absorb impacts, and distribute contact forces over large areas, making them inherently safe for manipulation of organs and human-robot interaction. Bioinspired exemplars include octopus-like arms and multi-arm underwater manipulators that achieve highly compliant locomotion and grasping through distributed actuation in elastomeric bodies [12]. Despite these advantages, fully soft architectures remain challenged by limited payload capacity, poor repeatability, and strong nonlinearities stemming from large deformations, viscoelasticity, and complex contact conditions. The modelling and control of soft continuum manipulators are further complicated by strong nonlinearities, hysteresis, and rate-dependent effects, which often require high-dimensional finite-element models or data-driven approximations [13]. In addition, many soft robotic structures rely on cast or 3D-printed elastomers with relatively low tear strength and fatigue resistance; under cyclic bending or contact-intensive tasks, these bodies may suffer from early crack initiation or material creep, which limits their lifetime in practical use [14, 15, 16, 17].

A number of recent works have therefore explored hybrid or variable-stiffness designs that combine rigid or semi-rigid backbones with compliant elements to obtain a better trade-off between stiffness, safety, and controllability [18, 11, 9]. In parallel, progress in additive manufacturing has enabled complex, multi-material geometries and rapid fabrication of intricate backbones and molds, which can subsequently be overmolded with silicone or other elastomers [17, 16]. These approaches show that soft-rigid integration can be exploited to localize compliance, tailor stiffness distributions, and embed sensing

or actuation channels inside structured backbones. Nevertheless, several important gaps remain. First, many existing designs either prioritize structural robustness but maintain a hard outer surface, or introduce a soft outer layer without systematically quantifying its impact on payload capacity, durability, and model fidelity. Second, comprehensive modelling frameworks that jointly consider tendon actuation, external forces, torsion, and distributed tendon–eyelet friction in multi-material, overmolded continuum structures are still scarce. Finally, experimental validation often focuses on basic kinematic characterization or tip-force measurements, while long-term durability under repeated bending and forceful interaction in the workspace is rarely quantified in a systematic way [3].

Motivated by these limitations, this work proposes a tendon-driven continuum robot architecture that integrates a 3D-printed rigid backbone with an overmolded silicone layer. The backbone is designed as a modular continuum structure that defines the kinematic skeleton, tendon routing, and nominal stiffness distribution, while the outer silicone layer provides a compliant, continuous contact surface that enhances safety and tolerates local deformations during interaction. The resulting hybrid design aims to retain the position accuracy and payload capacity of rigid-backbone continuum robots, while benefiting from the contact robustness and energy dissipation of soft robots. From a control perspective, the design preserves a relatively low-dimensional configuration space driven by tendon length changes, which facilitates model-based planning and control compared to fully soft bodies. From a mechanical perspective, the rigid backbone carries most of the bending and torsional loads, whereas the silicone encapsulation acts as a protective and damping shell that reduces stress concentrations at unit boundaries and tendon eyelets, and delays crack initiation during fatigue loading.

Building on this architecture, the main contributions of this paper are threefold. First, we introduce a novel tendon-driven continuum robot that combines a 3D-printed rigid backbone with an overmolded silicone body, specifically tailored to enhance payload capacity and structural durability while maintaining a soft external envelope for safe interaction. The design process and fabrication workflow leverage low-cost additive manufacturing for both the backbone and the molding tools, enabling reproducible production of complex geometries. Second, we develop a comprehensive mathematical model that relates tendon length changes to the robot configuration by accounting for bending, torsion, and tendon friction along the backbone, as well as external forces and moments applied at the tip. The model extends existing discretized Cosserat-rod and beam-constraint formulations [19, 20, 21] to explicitly incorporate capstan-like friction between tendons and eyelets [22] and to predict the load-dependent distribution of curvature and twist along the hybrid backbone. Third, we perform an extensive experimental characterization of the prototype, including trajectory tracking, hysteresis analysis, deformation under external loads, and force exertion capabilities throughout the reachable workspace. The results demonstrate that the proposed hybrid design achieves a favourable compromise between payload capacity, repeatability, and compliance, and that the developed model captures the main static behaviours under both unloaded and loaded conditions. Finally, we illustrate a representative application scenario in which the robot executes contact-rich tasks within a confined workspace, highlighting the potential of the proposed soft-rigid hybrid continuum manipulator for safe and effective medical and human-centered applications.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II details the robot’s fabrication process, including 3D printing and silicone casting. Section III presents the mathematical models. Experimental results and system integration are discussed in Sec-

Figure 1: Unit geometry and parameter definitions. (a) CAD model of an individual robot. (b) Top view of the unit.

tion IV. Section V concludes the study and outlines future directions.

2 Design and Fabrication

2.1 Unit Geometry and CAD Modeling

Table 1: SPECIFICATIONS OF TDCR

Parameter	Physical meaning	Value	Unit
l_u	The length of one unit	6	mm
l_{tot}	Total length of the bending section	96	mm
D_u	Outer diameter of a unit	7	mm
r_e	Radius of tendon routing circle	2.5	mm
D_l	Diameter of the central lumen	3	mm
D_R	Diameter of the TDCR	10	mm
n_{unit}	Number of units in the backbone	16	–
m_{robot}	Mass of the robot	8.36	g

This design combines the compliance of silicone with the structural integrity of 3D-printed segments. The continuum robot consists of identical units interconnected through

Figure 2: Silicone overmolding sequence for the backbone.

joint geometries with integrated low-friction tendon guide channels, with each rigid unit fully encapsulated in silicone to enhance mechanical performance. Tendons running through dedicated guide channels enable low-friction bending. It balances tendon routing space with load-bearing support. Iterative CAD refinements ensured a smooth outer contour and sufficient internal channels, while the rigid segment size was optimized to minimize volume without compromising stiffness. The specifications of TDCR are listed in Table 1.

2.2 Silicone Mold Design and Casting

Silicone was introduced to increase robot performance. In this work, we chose the silicone SILIXON 10 (Silikonfabrik, Germany). To ensure high-quality silicone casting, the fabrication process was performed as shown in Fig. 2. The details are listed below:

Step 1: Mount the rigid backbone and route the four tendons, which are preloaded in tendon channels (Fig. 2). Insert the positioning rod through the central lumen to ensure alignment. Step 2: Close the outer mold, fix the backbone in the mold through the positioning rod. Step 3: Prepare an addition-cure silicone solution, degas the silicone, and inject it from the bottom via the port to minimize bubbles and obtain a homogeneous body. After the silicone injection, allow it to cure at room temperature for 5 hours. Room-temperature curing avoids thermal warping of the units and preserves sheath alignment; elevated temperatures increased shrinkage and void formation in preliminary trials. Once fully cured, remove the mold halves. After removing the mold, the robot is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: The fabricated prototype of the soft-rigid hybrid TDCR.

2.3 Actuation Base Design

The actuation base (Fig. 4) was designed as a fully 3D-printed, modular platform that provides stable tendon actuation while remaining compact and easy to manufacture. It consists of two primary parts: a lower linear translation module and an upper housing that fixes and protects the drive components. The lower module is built around a linear rail that constrains motion to a single axis and ensures smooth, repeatable carriage translation along the indicated direction. The upper module is a rigid enclosure mounted on the carriage, which supports 4 servo motors for tendon length control and provides mechanical stiffness against reaction forces generated during pulling. In addition, a stepper motor is integrated to drive the linear motion, enabling precise displacement of the carriage along the rail. The overall architecture separates structural support (rail and carriage) from actuation and routing (motor housing and pulley), resulting in a robust, low-cost base that can be rapidly reproduced and iteratively refined through CAD updates and re-printing. Fig. 5 shows the assembled robot system.

In this work, we employ a 3D-printed polymer ball-joint backbone overmolded with silicone. Compared with [23] and [24], this polymer backbone with silicone overmold avoids bulky metallic components in the vicinity of the EM sensor and is therefore compatible with electromagnetic tracking, while the slender, non-ferromagnetic tendons did not measurably affect the Aurora EM tracker in our experiments. This soft-rigid hybrid design is expected to add compliance at inter-unit interfaces, potentially improve durability, and reduce the risk of buckling[25]. The rigid backbone can increase effective bending stiffness and may mitigate hysteresis compared with entirely soft bodies[26, 13].

Figure 4: CAD representation of the actuation base illustrating the arrangement of servo motors, stepper motor, and the linear rail mechanism.

Figure 5: Experimental Setup of Continuum Robot with Servo Motors, Microcontroller.

We state these as testable hypotheses and quantitatively assess durability, load capacity, hysteresis, and stability in the experiments presented later.

3 Mathematical Modeling

In this section, we derive a quasi-static model of the hybrid soft-rigid tendon-driven continuum robot used in this work. The backbone is discretized into rigid units that bend in orthogonal planes, while torsion and distributed tendon friction are explicitly taken into account. The resulting model maps commanded tendon length changes and

Figure 6: Anisotropic bending constraint and local frames. Consecutive units are mechanically constrained to bend in orthogonal planes: odd-index units bend about the local y-axis (plane x-z), while even-index units bend about the local x-axis (plane y-z).

an external tip load to the robot configuration.

3.1 Backbone Discretization and Coordinate Frames

The robot backbone is modeled as a sequence of N identical units of length ℓ_u , such that the total arc length is $L = N\ell_u$. The i -th unit occupies the interval $s \in [(i-1)\ell_u, i\ell_u]$ along the centerline. We attach a Cartesian frame $\{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z\}$ to the undeformed backbone at the base.

At the base of unit i , the backbone pose is described by a position vector and a rotation matrix: $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_i \in SO(3)$.

which transforms vectors from the local frame of unit i to the global frame. The pose at the tip of the unit is denoted by $(\mathbf{p}_{i+1}, \mathbf{R}_{i+1})$.

In the implementation, the rotation matrices \mathbf{R}_i are represented by unit quaternions \mathbf{q}_i for numerical robustness, and updated through quaternion multiplication based on axis-angle rotations. For clarity, we express the model in terms of \mathbf{R}_i and only mention quaternions where necessary.

3.2 Tendon Routing and Cross-Section Geometry

Each unit is actuated by four tendons routed through eyelets on a circle of radius r_e in the local cross-section. In the undeformed configuration, the tendon attachment points in the local frame of unit i are

$$\mathbf{r}_j = \begin{bmatrix} x_j \\ y_j \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = r_e \begin{bmatrix} \cos \beta_j \\ \sin \beta_j \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad j \in \{1, \dots, 4\}, \quad (1)$$

where β_j denotes the angular position of tendon j in the cross-section. In the prototype considered here,

$$\beta_1 = 0, \quad \beta_2 = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad \beta_3 = \pi, \quad \beta_4 = -\frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (2)$$

Let $T_{i,j}$ denote the tendon tension of tendon j at the *proximal* face of unit i , expressed in the local frame of that cross-section. By convention, positive tension pulls along the local $+\mathbf{e}_z$ direction.

3.3 Moments Induced by Tendon Tension and External Tip Load

3.3.1 Tendon-induced bending moment

Within one unit, the tendon is assumed to run approximately parallel to the backbone centerline, such that tendon j exerts a force

$$\mathbf{f}_{i,j} = -T_{i,j} \mathbf{e}_z \quad (3)$$

at the eyelet (force pointing towards the actuation side). The resulting moment about the backbone centerline at the base of unit i is

$$\mathbf{M}_i^{\text{ten}} = \sum_{j=1}^4 \mathbf{r}_j \times \mathbf{f}_{i,j} = \sum_{j=1}^4 \begin{bmatrix} -T_{i,j} y_j \\ T_{i,j} x_j \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

We denote its components in the local frame by

$$\mathbf{M}_i^{\text{ten}} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{x,i}^{\text{ten}} \\ M_{y,i}^{\text{ten}} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

3.3.2 Tip-load-induced bending and torsion

An external force $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ acts at the robot tip at $s = L$. In static equilibrium with a pure concentrated tip load and no distributed loads, the internal bending moment at arc length s is

$$\mathbf{M}^{\text{ext}}(s) = (\mathbf{p}(L) - \mathbf{p}(s)) \times \mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{p}(s)$ is the backbone centerline.

In the discrete model, we approximate (6) at the base of unit i as

$$\mathbf{M}_i^{\text{ext}} = (\mathbf{p}_{\text{tip}} - \mathbf{p}_i) \times \mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{p}_{tip} is the current estimate of the tip position, obtained from the previous iteration of the shape solver (Section 3.8).

For coupling with the local constitutive law, $\mathbf{M}_i^{\text{ext}}$ is expressed in the local frame of unit i via

$$\tilde{\mathbf{M}}_i^{\text{ext}} = \mathbf{R}_i^\top \mathbf{M}_i^{\text{ext}} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{x,i}^{\text{ext}} \\ M_{y,i}^{\text{ext}} \\ M_{z,i}^{\text{ext}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The total internal moment at the base of unit i in local coordinates is then

$$\mathbf{M}_i = \begin{bmatrix} M_{x,i} \\ M_{y,i} \\ M_{z,i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{x,i}^{\text{ten}} + M_{x,i}^{\text{ext}} \\ M_{y,i}^{\text{ten}} + M_{y,i}^{\text{ext}} \\ M_{z,i}^{\text{ext}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

The x - and y -components drive bending, whereas $M_{z,i}$ drives torsion.

3.4 Anisotropic Bending Constraint and Constant-Curvature Kinematics

The hybrid backbone design constrains each unit to bend only in a fixed plane, while consecutive units bend in orthogonal planes. Specifically,

- units with odd index i bend only around the local y -axis (bending plane x - z),
- units with even index i bend only around the local x -axis (bending plane y - z).

We denote the preferred bending axis of unit i in its local frame by

$$\mathbf{u}_p^{(i)} = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, & i \text{ odd,} \\ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, & i \text{ even.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Let \mathbf{M}_i be the total internal moment from (9). The bending is restricted to the projection of \mathbf{M}_i onto $\mathbf{u}_p^{(i)}$,

$$M_{u,i} = \mathbf{u}_p^{(i)\top} \mathbf{M}_i. \quad (11)$$

The out-of-plane component is assumed to be blocked by the mechanical structure.

Given the equivalent bending stiffness EI_{eq} , the curvature magnitude in unit i is

$$\kappa_i = \frac{|M_{u,i}|}{EI_{\text{eq}}}, \quad (12)$$

and the corresponding bending angle over the unit length is

$$\theta_i = \kappa_i \ell_u. \quad (13)$$

The sign of $M_{u,i}$ determines the direction of bending. The effective bending axis in the local frame is

$$\mathbf{u}_i = \text{sign}(M_{u,i}) \mathbf{u}_p^{(i)}. \quad (14)$$

For later use, we parameterize the bending-axis orientation by an angle ϕ_i in the x - y plane, defined by the projection of \mathbf{u}_i ,

$$\phi_i = \text{atan2}((\mathbf{u}_i)_y, (\mathbf{u}_i)_x). \quad (15)$$

The corresponding bending-plane direction in the cross-section is obtained by a $\pi/2$ rotation, i.e., $\psi_i = \phi_i + \pi/2; (\text{mod}; 2\pi)$.

3.4.1 Position update for one unit

Assuming constant curvature in unit i , the centerline segment forms a circular arc with curvature κ_i and bending angle θ_i in the plane defined by ϕ_i . In the local frame of unit i , the displacement of the unit tip relative to its base is given by the well-known constant-curvature relations (e.g., [20]). Due to the structural constraint, the bending-axis orientation ϕ_i only takes discrete values corresponding to $\pm\mathbf{e}_x$ or $\pm\mathbf{e}_y$, while (16), (17), (18) provide a unified constant-curvature displacement expression.

$$d_{x,i} = \frac{1 - \cos \theta_i}{\kappa_i} \sin \phi_i, \quad (16)$$

$$d_{y,i} = -\frac{1 - \cos \theta_i}{\kappa_i} \cos \phi_i, \quad (17)$$

$$d_{z,i} = \frac{\sin \theta_i}{\kappa_i}, \quad (18)$$

for $\kappa_i > 0$. In the (rare) case $|M_{u,i}| \approx 0$, we set $\kappa_i = 0$ and use the straight-segment limit

$$\mathbf{d}_i = \begin{bmatrix} d_{x,i} \\ d_{y,i} \\ d_{z,i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \ell_u \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

The global position update is then

$$\mathbf{p}_{i+1} = \mathbf{p}_i + \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{d}_i. \quad (20)$$

3.4.2 Orientation update for one unit

The relative rotation of unit i consists of bending by angle θ_i around axis \mathbf{u}_i and a twist (torsion) angle α_i about the local z -axis (discussed in the next subsection). The corresponding axis-angle representations are

$$(\mathbf{u}_i, \theta_i), \quad (\mathbf{e}_z, \alpha_i), \quad (21)$$

and the combined relative rotation is

$$\mathbf{R}_i^{\text{rel}} = \exp(\theta_i[\mathbf{u}_i]_{\times}) \exp(\alpha_i[\mathbf{e}_z]_{\times}), \quad (22)$$

where $[\cdot]_{\times}$ denotes the skew-symmetric matrix representation of the cross product. The relative rotation is composed of bending about \mathbf{u}_i followed by a twist α_i about the (local) axial direction \mathbf{e}_z of the unit.

The orientation update is then

$$\mathbf{R}_{i+1} = \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{R}_i^{\text{rel}}. \quad (23)$$

In the implementation, (22) is realized via unit quaternions \mathbf{q}_i and quaternion multiplication.

3.5 Torsional Deformation

The external tip load generally produces a non-zero torsional moment $M_{z,i}$ for unit i through (6). Assuming linear torsional elasticity with equivalent torsional stiffness GJ_{eq} , the average twist rate in unit i is

$$\tau_i = \frac{M_{z,i}}{GJ_{\text{eq}}}. \quad (24)$$

The corresponding twist angle accumulated over the unit length is

$$\alpha_i = \tau_i \ell_u = \frac{M_{z,i} \ell_u}{GJ_{\text{eq}}}. \quad (25)$$

The sequence $\{\alpha_i\}_{i=1}^N$ is used both for the orientation update (22) and for evaluating the cumulative torsion along the robot.

3.6 Tendon Length Change

For unit i with curvature κ_i and bending-plane angle ϕ_i , the tendon length change $\Delta\ell_{i,j}$ of tendon j relative to the backbone centerline over that unit can be derived geometrically from the constant-curvature assumption. Denote the unit-length backbone tangent direction in the bending plane by

$$\mathbf{b}_i = \begin{bmatrix} -\sin \phi_i \\ \cos \phi_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (26)$$

which is orthogonal to the projection of the bending axis. Then the length change of tendon j over unit i is

$$\Delta\ell_{i,j} = -\theta_i \mathbf{r}_j^\top \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = -\theta_i (x_j(-\sin \phi_i) + y_j \cos \phi_i). \quad (27)$$

The total length change for tendon j over the entire backbone is the sum over all units,

$$\Delta\ell_j = \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta\ell_{i,j}. \quad (28)$$

Given commanded tendon length changes $\Delta\ell_j^*$ at the base, the static problem consists of finding base tensions $T_{1,j}$ and the corresponding configuration such that

$$\Delta\ell_j(T_{1,1}, \dots, T_{1,4}) \approx \Delta\ell_j^*, \quad (29)$$

subject to the anisotropic bending constraint, torsion, and frictional tension loss along the backbone.

3.7 Capstan Friction Model Along the Backbone

3.7.1 Discrete capstan relation

Tendon friction at the tendon–eyelet interface is modeled by a capstan-type relation. For a flexible tendon sliding over a curved surface with friction coefficient μ , the classical capstan equation relates the tension at two ends of a wrap with angle Φ as [27]:

$$T_{\text{out}} = T_{\text{in}} \exp(-\mu|\Phi|), \quad (30)$$

where $\Phi > 0$ corresponds to the total wrap angle accumulated along the contact.

In our model, the tendon is constrained by a sequence of discrete eyelets and integrated silicone, and the contact curvature in each unit is constant. For unit i with bending angle θ_i and bending-plane angle ϕ_i , the effective wrap angle increment experienced by tendon j is obtained by projecting the curvature onto the direction of tendon j in the cross-section,

$$\Delta\phi_{i,j} = \theta_i \cos(\beta_j - \psi_i), \quad \psi_i = \phi_i + \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (31)$$

This expression reflects that a tendon located in the bending plane ($\beta_j \approx \psi_i$) experiences the full local curvature, whereas a tendon aligned with the bending axis ($\beta_j \approx \phi_i$) experiences negligible wrapping.

Using (30) with the discrete increments (31), the tension at the distal end of unit i for tendon j is related to the proximal tension via

$$T_{i+1,j} = T_{i,j} \exp(-\mu |\Delta\phi_{i,j}|). \quad (32)$$

Equation (32) is used to propagate tendon tensions along the backbone, starting from the base tensions $T_{1,j}$.

3.7.2 Experimental identification of the friction coefficient

The friction coefficient μ appearing in (32) is not assumed a priori; instead, it is identified experimentally using a single-tendon calibration experiment inspired by the capstan methodology in [27].

In the calibration experiment, only one tendon (say $j = 1$) is actuated, while the others are kept slack. For a sequence of quasi-static configurations indexed by k , we record:

- the proximal tendon tension $T_{\text{in}}^{(k)}$ using force gauge,
- the backbone centerline $\mathbf{p}^{(k)}(s)$ using a Faro measurement arm.

From the measured centerline $\mathbf{p}^{(k)}(s)$ we reconstruct the discrete curvature and bending-plane angles $\{\theta_i^{(k)}, \phi_i^{(k)}\}_{i=1}^N$ by fitting constant-curvature segments of length ℓ_u between neighboring sample points. For tendon $j = 1$, the effective wrap angle of configuration k is then

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi^{(k)} &= \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \Delta\phi_{i,1}^{(k)} \right| \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \theta_i^{(k)} \cos(\beta_1 - \psi_i^{(k)}) \right| \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \theta_i^{(k)} \sin(\beta_1 - \phi_i^{(k)}) \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

During the calibration, the tendon is routed such that the distal tension $T_{\text{out}}^{(k)}$ is known (e.g., by attaching it to a second load cell or a calibrated weight). For each configuration k , the classical capstan relation predicts

$$\log \frac{T_{\text{in}}^{(k)}}{T_{\text{out}}^{(k)}} = \mu \Phi^{(k)} + \varepsilon^{(k)}, \quad (34)$$

where $\varepsilon^{(k)}$ collects modeling and measurement errors. Stacking (34) over K configurations leads to a linear least-squares problem in μ ,

$$\hat{\mu} = \arg \min_{\mu} \sum_{k=1}^K \left(\log \frac{T_{\text{in}}^{(k)}}{T_{\text{out}}^{(k)}} - \mu \Phi^{(k)} \right)^2. \quad (35)$$

The closed-form solution is

$$\hat{\mu} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K \Phi^{(k)} \log(T_{\text{in}}^{(k)}/T_{\text{out}}^{(k)})}{\sum_{k=1}^K (\Phi^{(k)})^2}. \quad (36)$$

The identified coefficient $\hat{\mu}$ is subsequently used as a fixed parameter in the multi-tendon statics model via (32). This procedure ensures that the friction model is consistent with the actual backbone geometry and tendon routing of the robot.

3.8 Inverse Statics With Friction and External Load

For a given external tip load \mathbf{F}_{ext} and commanded tendon length changes $\Delta \ell_j^*$, the inverse statics problem consists of finding base tensions $\mathbf{T}_1 = [T_{1,1}, \dots, T_{1,4}]^\top$ and a backbone configuration $\{\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{R}_i\}_{i=1}^{N+1}$ such that

$$\Delta \ell_j(\mathbf{T}_1, \mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}) \approx \Delta \ell_j^*, \quad j = 1, \dots, 4, \quad (37)$$

under the anisotropic bending constraint and the frictional tension propagation (32) with $\mu = \hat{\mu}$.

The solution is computed numerically using a nested scheme, the process of computation is summarized in Algorithm 1.

This nested procedure yields a static configuration that is consistent with the measured friction coefficient, the anisotropic bending behavior of the hybrid backbone, the torsional response, and the prescribed external tip load.

4 Experimental Evaluation and Validation

This section provides an integrated experimental evaluation of the proposed soft-rigid hybrid TDCR. The experiments are organized into four parts: (i) trajectory-level validation together with a first dynamic response characterization; (ii) payload capacity evaluation; (iii) hysteresis and durability characterization; (iv) proof-of-concept application demonstrations. Unless otherwise specified, all tests were conducted quasi-statically to reduce rate-dependent effects and isolate the structural and frictional behaviors.

The TDCR is installed on an actuation base manufactured using 3D printing (see Fig. 7), including four servo motors (DS3218 digital servo motors, Miuzei), controlled by an Arduino Uno microcontroller. The TDCR with the actuation base is located on the track board of the EM tracking system. A 6-DOF EM sensor is placed in the lumen of the tip unit, and the second EM sensor is placed on the base as the reference coordinate system. The force gauge (GOYOJO Digital Force Gauge, 50 N range, resolution 0.01 N) is used to measure force on the tip of TDCR.

Algorithm 1 Inverse Statics with Friction and External Load

- 1: **Given** Target tendon lengths $\{\Delta\ell_j^*\}$, external load $\mathbf{F}_{\text{external}}$, tolerances $\epsilon_{\text{shape}}, \epsilon_{\text{len}}$.
 - 2: **Initialize** Base tensions $\mathbf{T}_1 \leftarrow \mathbf{T}_{\text{init}}$.
 - 3: **repeat**
 - 4: // Inner Loop: Fixed-point shape iteration
 - 5: **repeat**
 - 6: Propagate tendon tensions $\{T_{i,j}\}$ along the backbone via the discrete capstan model (32) using $\hat{\mu}$.
 - 7: Compute internal moments \mathbf{M}_i via (4)–(9) based on current tip estimate \mathbf{p}_{tip} .
 - 8: Calculate deformations $\{\theta_i, \alpha_i\}$ and update backbone poses $\{\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{R}_i\}$ via kinematics (20)–(23).
 - 9: **until** Tip position change $\|\Delta\mathbf{p}_{\text{tip}}\| < \epsilon_{\text{shape}}$
 - 10: // Outer Loop: Root-finding for base tensions
 - 11: Compute resulting tendon length changes $\Delta\ell_j(\mathbf{T}_1)$ via geometric integration (27) and (28).
 - 12: **Update** \mathbf{T}_1 to minimize residuals $\mathbf{e} = \Delta\ell(\mathbf{T}_1) - \Delta\ell^*$ (e.g., Levenberg–Marquardt step).
 - 13: **until** Length residuals $\|\mathbf{e}\| < \epsilon_{\text{len}}$
 - 14: **Output** Converged base tensions \mathbf{T}_1^* and robot shape.
-

Figure 7: robot system with EM tracking.

4.1 Trajectory-level Validation

We first quantify the accuracy of the load-free mathematical map in the position-controlled regime, in which the tendons are driven in length control and external forces are negligible. Tendon length change is controlled by servo motors. We recorded the actuated-unit

bending angle and the tip Cartesian position. The comparison between measurements and simulations is shown in Fig. 8–9.

Across the tested range, the bending angle grows approximately linearly with ΔL , while departures at larger tendon-length changes likely stem from unmodeled friction, elasticity, and slight slack. To evaluate the results, the primary metric used is the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between the simulated positions (P_{sim}) and the experimentally measured positions (P_{exp}) along the trajectory, calculated as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (p_{\text{sim},i} - p_{\text{exp},i})^2}. \quad (38)$$

$$\text{nRMSE} = \frac{\text{RMSE}}{L_{\text{ref}}} \times 100\%, \quad (39)$$

where N is the number of measured points, and L_{ref} is the reference length for normalization. In this paper we set $L_{\text{ref}} = l_{\text{tot}} = 96$ mm. The RMSE is 5.71 mm (nRMSE 5.95%). The maximum absolute tip-position error e_{max} observed in this experiment was 8.17 mm, corresponding to 8.51% of the L_{ref} .

To provide a first indication of the dynamic behavior and reaction time of the prototype, we characterized the tip bending angle in response to a step-like tendon actuation. Starting from the straight configuration, the actuation unit was commanded to pull the tendon from zero to a certain length to make the tip bending angle around 120 degrees, and the resulting tip angle $\theta_{\text{tip}}(t)$ was recorded. As shown in Fig. 10, the tip angle increases almost linearly and reaches its final value of approximately $\theta_{\text{tip}} \approx 114.59^\circ$ after about 0.67 s, with no significant overshoot or oscillations.

4.2 Payload Capacity Evaluation

This experiment characterizes the load-bearing capability of the proposed TDCR by quantifying the payload-induced deformation at the tip. The robot was mounted horizontally on a rigid fixture, and all tendons were initialized with the same minimal pretension to ensure a repeatable, straight reference posture. Calibrated weights from 1 g to 20 g were sequentially attached at the tip. After a 30 s dwell time to mitigate viscoelastic settling effects, the tip pose was captured by the EM tracker. The Euclidean tip displacement was computed with respect to the unloaded reference as $\Delta p = \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_0\|$, and the corresponding tip bending angle was extracted consistently from the measured tip orientation.

As shown in Fig. 11, both Δp and the tip bending angle increase monotonically with payload, indicating a stable and predictable deformation response. Under the maximum tested payload of 20 g, the measured tip displacement reaches 10.6 mm, with a corresponding tip bending angle of approximately 38° . The simulated curves follow the same trend and remain close to the measured results over the entire loading range, supporting the validity of the model for payload-dependent deformation prediction.

4.3 Hysteresis and Durability Characterization

4.3.1 Hysteresis Characterization

To evaluate the energy loss and positional accuracy during cyclic motion, we quantified the hysteresis of each design. Hysteresis in TDCRs primarily stems from internal material

Figure 8: Comparison of model simulation and experimental data: Robot profiles in the space.

Figure 9: Tip bending angle vs. commanded tendon length change.

Figure 10: Tip bending angle response $\theta_{\text{tip}}(t)$ to tendon actuation.

Figure 11: Payload-dependent deformation response of the continuum robot. Left: Euclidean tip displacement as a function of applied payload (0–20 g). Right: corresponding tip bending angle versus payload.

damping and inter-component friction, leading to a mismatch between actuation input and robot posture. Each robot was actuated using a single tendon to bend from a straight configuration ($\theta = 0^\circ$) to a tip bending angle of $\theta = 100^\circ$ and then return to the initial state. The motion was performed quasi-statically to minimize dynamic effects. During the cycle, we simultaneously recorded the tendon length (Δl), the base tendon tension (T_{base}), and the tip bending angle (θ) using the force gauge and the EM tracker, respectively. After two pre-conditioning cycles, three consecutive loading-unloading cycles were recorded for analysis.

Hysteresis was quantified by the energy lost per cycle, which we computed as the closed-loop area in the $T_{\text{base}}-\Delta l$ plane,

$$E_{\text{hys}} = \oint T_{\text{base}} d(\Delta l) \quad [\text{N mm}] \quad (40)$$

estimated via trapezoidal integration over the loading and unloading branches. To enable fair comparison when $\theta_{\text{min}} > 0^\circ$ or θ_{max} deviates from the nominal 100° , the actual angular excursion

$$\Delta\theta_{\text{range}} = \theta_{\text{max}} - \theta_{\text{min}} \quad (41)$$

Figure 12: Hysteresis loops in the tension-tendon length change space during a bending cycle.

was used for normalization:

$$A_{\text{hys}} = \frac{E_{\text{hys}}}{\Delta\theta_{\text{range}}} \quad [\text{N mm/deg}]. \quad (42)$$

The results are shown in Fig. 12. The proposed design exhibits a small hysteresis loop under the tested loading–unloading cycle. The measured energy loss per cycle, quantified by the enclosed loop area, is $E_{\text{hys}} = 5.96 \text{ N mm}$, corresponding to a normalized hysteresis area of $A_{\text{hys}} = 0.07 \text{ N mm/deg}$. These results are consistent with reduced hysteretic effects in the hybrid soft–rigid structure, arising from both material viscoelasticity and tendon–channel friction.

4.3.2 Durability Characterization

This experiment assesses the mechanical durability and performance consistency under prolonged, large-deformation cyclic loading. The TDCR was subjected to cyclic, bi-directional planar bending using actuation base. A peak-to-peak swing of approximately 200° (from -100° to $+100^\circ$) was targeted. The required tendon length change to achieve this initial range was recorded and kept constant throughout the test. Specimens were driven at a quasi-static rate. Using the EM trackers, we continuously logged the tip bending angle to extract the achieved peak angles in the left and right directions, $\theta_L(c)$ and $\theta_R(c)$, for each cycle c . From this data, we calculated two primary metrics:

- Mean Angle $\alpha(c)$: After extracting the signed peak angles in the left and right directions, we define the mean angle at cycle c as:

$$\alpha(c) = \frac{\theta_L(c) + \theta_R(c)}{2}. \quad (43)$$

- Symmetry Error $S_{\text{sym}}(c)$: The absolute difference between left and right peak angles, indicating kinematic drift.

$$S_{\text{sym}}(c) = ||\theta_L(c)| - |\theta_R(c)|| \quad (44)$$

The durability test results are shown in Fig.13. The proposed design maintains a relatively stable $\alpha(c)$ with consistently small $S_{\text{sym}}(c)$ throughout 200 cycles, indicating stable amplitude and near-symmetric left–right response. The silicone overmolding and rigid

Figure 13: Durability test results under cyclic bending. Peak bending angles measured over 200 actuation cycles, reported for left bending (θ_L), right bending (θ_R), and their average mean ((θ_L, θ_R)). The nearly constant peak angles across cycles indicate stable bending amplitude with minimal drift, evidencing good durability under repeated loading.

backbone structure effectively distribute stress across the unit interfaces, preventing the localized stress concentrations that led to failure. Simultaneously, the internal rigid backbone can prevent the large-scale material fatigue. This experiment provides empirical evidence that our soft-rigid hybrid architecture achieves a synergistic combination of flexibility and resilience, leading to a longer operational lifespan.

4.4 Application Demonstrations

To illustrate task-oriented capabilities beyond benchmark characterization, we demonstrate two representative use cases that leverage the hybrid soft-rigid structure and the integrated central lumen. First, we evaluate interaction performance in a confined workspace, where the robot must bend and exert contact forces while maintaining a compact footprint. Under quasi-static bending inside the constrained environment, the distal end generates a maximum contact force of 1.34 N (see Fig.14). Importantly, the peak force remains nearly invariant across bending directions, indicating that the mechanical output is largely insensitive to the contact orientation. This directional consistency is practically valuable for confined-space manipulation because it reduces the need for direction-dependent calibration and enables more predictable interaction forces during probing, pushing, or tissue-safe palpation-like behaviors.

Second, we demonstrate tool-carrying and payload robustness during large-curvature motions (see Fig.15). The central lumen provides a direct pathway for task accessories (e.g., biopsy forceps or imaging components), enabling the robot to function as a steerable delivery conduit rather than a pure positioning device. In the presented setup, the robot performs high-curvature bending while carrying an external 20 g payload attached at the distal region, maintaining smooth and stable motion without abrupt posture degradation. This behavior reflects the intended design balance: a compliant silicone exterior for safe contact and impact tolerance, combined with a load-bearing internal backbone that preserves bending authority under practical tool-related loads.

Figure 14: Contact-force measurement setup for the TDCR. The robot tip is brought into contact with a digital force gauge to quantify the maximum achievable contact force during quasi-static loading. Two representative configurations are shown, illustrating force measurements under different contact locations/orientations while maintaining the same actuation conditions.

Figure 15: Application demonstrations of the soft-rigid hybrid TDCR. (a) Large-curvature bending of the robot in a hook-like configuration. (b) Compliant tip interaction and manipulation using the distal end. (c) Proof-of-concept deployment in a confined workspace, illustrating the robot’s ability to reach around obstacles while maintaining a small cross-section and safe physical interaction.

Together, these demonstrations support the robot’s suitability for constrained, contact-rich environments where both controllable interaction forces and through-lumen tool compatibility are required, such as endoluminal inspection and basic interventional assistance.

5 Conclusion

This work presented a multimaterial soft–rigid tendon-driven continuum robot that combines a 3D-printed segmented backbone with silicone overmolding to improve durability and payload capacity while preserving a compliant, tissue-safe exterior. The prototype (10 mm outer diameter with a 3 mm central lumen) was integrated with a compact, fully 3D-printed actuation base and evaluated using EM tracking. To support model-based design and analysis, we developed a quasi-static framework that maps commanded tendon length changes to robot shape while accounting for anisotropic bending constraints, torsion, distributed capstan-like tendon–eyelet friction, and external tip loading.

Experiments demonstrated that the proposed model captures the dominant static behaviors of the robot in position-controlled operation. In trajectory-level validation, the model achieved an RMSE of 5.71 mm (normalized RMSE 5.95% using a 96 mm reference length), with a maximum absolute tip-position error of 8.17 mm (8.51%). A first dynamic response characterization further showed a fast and well-damped actuation behavior: the tip bending angle increased nearly linearly and reached approximately 114.59° within about 0.67 s, without noticeable overshoot or oscillation. Payload testing confirmed a balanced stiffness–compliance trade-off; under a 20 g tip load, the robot exhibited a tip deflection of 10.6 mm. Hysteresis characterization indicated low energy loss, with an enclosed loop area of 5.96 N·mm and a normalized hysteresis metric $A_{\text{hys}} = 0.07$ N·mm/deg over a 0 – 100° bending cycle. Durability tests under repeated large-amplitude bending (approximately -100° to $+100^\circ$) showed stable peak angles and near-symmetric left–right response across 200 cycles, evidencing consistent performance under cyclic loading. Finally, application demonstrations highlighted practical contact-rich operation: the robot generated up to 1.34 N contact force in confined-space interaction with minimal directional dependence, and maintained smooth high-curvature motion while carrying a 20 g distal payload and supporting through-lumen tool deployment.

Future work will extend this platform toward richer task execution, improved parameter identification under varying environmental contact, and expanded modeling to incorporate rate-dependent viscoelastic effects and more complex tool–tissue interactions.

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